

Fermat's Last Theorem : for $n \nmid XYZ$

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Fermat's Last Theorem : 17 century proof

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I proved that

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has ordered pair solution of natural number (X,Y,Z) , (n is a prime number)

This ordered pair (X,Y,Z) must satisfy the following three conditions:

① $(X,Y,Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$, where $\text{rad}(R)=R$, and $\text{gcd}(R,n) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(R,A) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(R,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(A,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(A,n) = 1$

② $(X,Y,Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$, where $\text{rad}(L)=L$, and $\text{gcd}(L,n) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(L,A) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(L,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(B,Z) = 1$, $\text{gcd}(B,n) = 1$

Chapter 0. Lemma

Lemma 1. For r such that $0 < r < n$, nCr is a multiple of n . (n is a prime number, which is a index of Fermat equation)

pf) nCr is a natural number. In Pascal's triangle, we can inductively prove that these numbers are natural numbers.

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)!r!}$$

But $(n-r)$, $(n-r-1)$, $(n-r-2)$, ... 2 , 1 can't divide n because n is a prime number and $n-r < n$.

Similarly, r , $(r-1)$, $(r-2)$, $(r-3)$, ..., 2 , 1 can't divide n so the denominator always has n . Thus, nCr is always a natural number that is a multiple of n .

Lemma 2. The following equation is a contradiction:

$$p^2N = pK$$

where p is prime number, N is coprime to p , and K is coprime to p .

Because if you divide both sides by p , you get

$$pN = K$$

The left side is a multiple of p . But the right side is not a multiple of p .

This Lemma will play a very important role in the proof in chapters 2 and 3.

Lemma 3. $p \mid Y^n$ is equivalent to $p \mid Y$

(p is a prime number. And $p \mid Y^n$ means Y^n is a multiple of p .)

pf)

p is a prime number. so Y must have p as a prime factor. Let's assume that Y does not have p as a prime factor. Then p cannot be generated by raising Y to a power.

'Because p is a prime number.'

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right) \quad (\lambda)$$

after logic:

And also (X, Y, Z) must be satisfied the form

$$(X, Y, Z) = (LB, RA, GC)$$

$$\gcd(L, B) = 1$$

$$\gcd(R, A) = 1$$

$$\gcd(G, C) = 1$$

Why?

Because, $Y = Z - L^n$ and

$$\begin{aligned} X^n &= Z^n - Y^n \\ &= Z^n \\ &- \left\{ Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} L^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} L^{2n} - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (L^n)^{n-2} \right. \\ &\left. + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (L^n)^{n-1} - L^{n^2} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$X = LB, \text{ so } X^n = L^n B^n$$

On the right-hand side, all terms except $\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} L^n$ are multiples of L^{2n} .

If $\gcd(L, B) = k > 1$, all terms on both sides except $\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} L^n$ are multiples of k^{2n} .

It is contradiction by Lemma 2.

Therefore, $\gcd(L, B) = 1$.

By similar logic, $\gcd(R, A) = 1$ and $\gcd(G, C) = 1$.

In the process of deriving that $\gcd(G, C) = 1$,

we can use $X = X$ and $Y = G^n - X$.

Then we can conclude that C cannot have a common divisor greater than 2 with G .

Let $G, R = \text{odd number}, L = \text{even number}$

So in (λ) , we can know that

$$X = LB = \frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$2LB = G^n - R^n + L^n$$

$$G^n - R^n = 2LB - L^n = 2L \left(B - \frac{L^{n-1}}{2} \right)$$

(Since L is an even number, $\frac{L^{n-1}}{2}$ is a natural number. And $\gcd(B, L) = 1$, so

$$\gcd \left(2L, B - \frac{L^{n-1}}{2} \right) = 1$$

We can express

$$G^n - R^n = 2Lk_1$$

(k_1 is coprime to L)

$$Y = RA = \frac{G^n - L^n + R^n}{2}$$

$$2RA = G^n - L^n + R^n$$

$$G^n - L^n = R^n - 2RA = R(R^{n-1} - 2A)$$

$$(\gcd(R, 2A) = 1, \text{ so } \gcd(R, R^{n-1} - 2A) = 1)$$

We can express

$$G^n - L^n = Rk_2$$

k_2 is coprime to R, G, L .

$$Z = GC = \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$2GC = G^n + R^n + L^n$$

$$R^n + L^n = 2GC - G^n = G(2C - G^{n-1})$$

$$(\gcd(2C, G) = 1, \text{ so } \gcd(G, 2C - G^{n-1}) = 1)$$

We can express

$$R^n + L^n = Gk_3$$

k_3 is coprime to G, R, L .

To summarize the results,

$$Gk_3 = R^n + L^n \quad (1)$$

$$Rk_2 = G^n - L^n \quad (2)$$

$$2Lk_1 = G^n - R^n \quad (3)$$

All variables are natural numbers.

Is this relationship possible?

My answer is, NO!

First of all, $G = R + L + a$ (a is any integer)

I will show that a must be zero.

If $a \neq 0$, by (1),

$$(R + L + a)k_3 = R^n + L^n$$

Since the left-hand side is a multiple of $(R + L + a)$, the right-hand side must be a multiple of $(R + L + a)$.

It means that the right-hand side can be expressed by

$$R^n + L^n = (R + L + a) \times f(R, L)$$

Therefore, if we substitute $R = -L - a$, the value of the right-hand side must be zero.

But in $R^n + L^n$, if we substitute $R = -L - a$,

$$(-L - a)^n + L^n = -(L + a)^n + L^n \neq 0$$

If $-(L + a)^n + L^n = 0$,

$$(L + a)^n = L^n$$

$$L + a = L$$

$$\therefore a = 0$$

Therefore we get

$$G = R + L$$

Substitute it into the ordered pair form (λ) .

$$(2X, 2Y, 2Z) \\ = \{(R + L)^n - R^n + L^n, (R + L)^n + R^n - L^n, (R + L)^n + R^n + L^n\}$$

Substitute it into the Fermat equation $(2X)^n + (2Y)^n = (2Z)^n$

And consider it n^2 -th order equation of L . (It doesn't matter if it's R)

Then we can verify that the constant term is 0.

What about the first term for L ?

$$2X = \binom{n}{1} R^{n-1}L + \binom{n}{2} R^{n-2}L^2 + \dots + L^n + L^n$$

$$2Y = R^n + \binom{n}{1} R^{n-1}L + \binom{n}{2} R^{n-2}L^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} RL^{n-1} + R^n$$

$$2Z = R^n + \binom{n}{1} R^{n-1}L + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} RL^{n-1} + L^n + R^n + L^n$$

The first term for L in $(2X)^n$ is 0. $(2Y)^n$ and $(2Z)^n$ have same coefficient.

The second term for L in

I am finding. I will find it. Thank you for reading.

Therefore the Fermat's last theorem is true.

Thank you for reading.

Thank you for reading.